

Title: Open Data as a benefit for the Government itself

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INTRODUCTION:

The Netherlands is a leading country on supplying data as open data. For multiple years, The Netherlands is within the top 10 scoring countries worldwide on open data. What does it bring? What does it bring Government itself?

AIM:

To get open data as a crucial element of policymaking within Governments.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Multiple experiments on working with open data in policy making areas are in progress. Dealing with depopulation in certain area's, employment growth, democratic challenges are experimented with to get a deeper understanding of the role of data in these processes.

RESULTS:

More data comes available as open data by encouraging results from these experiments. Working with data in policy making processes will increase.

CONCLUSIONS:

KEYWORDS:

Open data, policy making, democratic effects of open data

BIOGRAPHY:

Paul Suijkerbuijk is the driving force behind open data in the Netherlands.

In this role, over the last few years he has managed to create an unprecedented momentum in the Dutch open data community, convincing governments to open up and share their data and optimizing the preconditions for open data to take off.

Paul is the founder of data.overheid.nl the dutch open data portal which is launched in beta in 2010. Currently data.overheid.nl is giving access to more than 10.000 open data sets in the Netherlands and still counting.

Open data is about value, Paul is constantly challenging government, society and industry to work together to find this value. It can be social value, economical value or democratic value.

However, the biggest value is on cooperation, finding new ways of working together to find innovative solutions.

Paul is also working for the European Commission as a Horizon 2020 Evaluator and Reviewer

Paul has a technical background in physics.